

AIRBORNE SOUND INSULATION DESCRIPTOR EQUALLY VALID FOR LIGHT-WEIGHT AND MASONRY BUILDING TECHNIQUE

Herbert Muellner and Jakub Banklewski

*Versuchsanstalt TGM, Fachbereich Akustik und Bauphysik, Wexstrasse 19-23, A-1200 Wien, Austria
email: hmuellner@tgm.ac.at*

Monika Rychtáriková

KU Leuven, Faculty of Architecture, A&T, Hoogstraat 51, 9000 Gent, Belgium,

Kristian Jambrošić

University of Zagreb, Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Computing, Unska 3, HR-10000 Zagreb, Croatia

Vojtech Chmelík and Lukáš Zelem

STU Bratislava, Faculty of Civil Engineering, Department of Building Construction, Radlinského 11, 81005 Bratislava, Slovakia

Daniel Urbán

A&Z Acoustics s.r.o., Repašského 2, 84102 Bratislava, Slovakia,

Christ Glorieux

Laboratory of Acoustics, Soft Matter and Biophysics, Celestijnenlaan 200D, B-3001 Leuven, Belgium

Sound insulation rating systems for characterizing sound insulation performance of building elements should be in close relation to contemporary building practices and living aspects. An appropriate single number quantity system has to represent sound insulation properties from the physical as well as from the perceptual point of view, equally regarding all of the currently applied building techniques. It is necessary to prove that none of the building modes are disadvantaged by single number ratings. In an experimental listening test setting, subjects had to compare the loudness of sound stimuli filtered by a prototypical lightweight and masonry wall sound insulation characteristic considering the frequency range from 50 Hz to 5000 Hz. The stimuli were judged by the test persons in order to find equally loud pairs of both the masonry and the lightweight walls. The single number value, based on an adapted reference spectrum close to the 90% hearing threshold below 100 Hz, showed the smallest differences in comparison to the currently applied descriptors according to ISO 717-1 which include frequencies down to 50 Hz.

Keywords: sound insulation, loudness, subjective perception, listening tests, single number quantity

1. Introduction

The challenge to characterize acoustical living comfort as best as possible remains in the field of building acoustics. Due to a wide range of psychological factors, it is difficult to define requirements

and descriptors to be able to cover all claims in the same way. Currently, there is no generally applicable assessment instrument, which would be sufficiently closely interrelated with the actual physical sound insulation [1] based on the noise assessments expressed by the occupants. There are no standardized psychoacoustic test procedures for building acoustic problems, which would allow reliable quantification of the perceived sound insulation quality.

The study of Vian et al. [2] shows that there was a need for expressing subjective opinion on sound coming through partition walls since early 1980s. Recently, subjective laboratory listening tests have become a very popular tool in the process of understanding, verifying and determining reliable objective acoustical parameters for sound insulation assessment [3, 4].

The lifestyle has changed as well as the quality of life in the course of the last decades. In the same time, the variety of construction methods has grown. This diversity requires correspondingly differentiated approaches with regard to building physics. Some voices were being raised already in the middle and the end of the 1990s [5, 6], asking for an adaptation of given requirements for the noise protection. It was criticized that the structural acoustic frequency range is not broad enough and, in particular, that the low frequency range should be included in the consideration. Corresponding studies have underlined the need for these changes to be included within the framework of suitable noise protection requirements and modernized descriptors [7, 8, 9].

This article shows results from subjective laboratory listening tests regarding investigation of correlation between objective loudness difference of perceived stimuli and subjective perception of the loudness as well as comparison with objective single number quantities used for assessment of sound insulation between dwellings with focus on extended frequency range down to 50 Hz.

2. Laboratory listening tests

2.1 Description of selected wall filters

The selection of prototypical wall spectra was based on results from standard tests performed in wall sound insulation test facility of the TGM institute in period from 2004 to 2015. However, only those results were selected, which were apparently installed in the test stand without any significant processing errors (e.g. leaking connections), as well as frequency range down to 50 Hz was taken into account during the measurement. In addition, only those types of wall have been selected which have a weighted sound reduction index R_w of more than 45 dB in order to be able to cover a sound insulation area relevant to residential construction. The average sound insulation was determined from the selected results, which in the further investigations were used as a typical construction characteristics filter for creating sound stimuli for listening tests. Figure 1 shows the most unfavourable, the most favourable as well as the average sound attenuation measurements as a function of frequency for both LW (lightweight) and HW (heavyweight) walls.

2.2 Listening stimuli filtering

The idea behind stimuli used in listening tests was to simulate situations as close as possible to reality. Two sound files were used for further filtering: (i) pink noise with length of 2 s, and (ii) a piece of music with significant low frequency levels of 5 s length. The music piece was the song “Highway to Hell” by ACDC. It has a pronounced temporal fluctuation in the lower frequency range in comparison with pink noise, Figure 2. Both stimuli were processed in order to have similar average frequency spectra. These stimuli have already been used in previous similar experiments [10, 11]. Table 1 shows loudness and A-weighted sound pressure level values of stimuli before filtering. Subsequently, these two original sounds were filtered by two different types of simulated walls – lightweight (LW) wall and masonry/heavyweight (HW) wall that were described in previous chapter 2.1. Filtering was done in 2 dB steps for LW wall in a sound insulation range of $R_w = 48$ dB to $R_w = 62$ dB and for HW wall in range of $R_w = 43$ dB to $R_w = 57$ dB, which resulted with eight different sound insulation situation for both walls, or 16 different sound stimuli altogether. The pink noise level reduction range was chosen according to $R_w + C_{50-5000}$, corresponding to a range between 42 dB and 56

dB. The sound insulation range of the two wall types was selected in a way that stimuli filtered by corresponding wall combinations had approximately the same loudness.

Figure 1: The average sound insulation characteristics for typical HW (red) and LW (blue) walls. Thick lines represent the average sound insulation while the thin lines show the best and the worst sound insulation curve used.

Figure 2: Spectrogram of the used sound stimuli: pink noise (left) and “Highway to Hell” (right).

Table 1: Loudness N (son) and A-weighted sound pressure level L (dB(A)) of the presented stimuli before filtering.

	ACDC		Pink Noise	
	N/s	$L/dB(A)$	N/s	$L/dB(A)$
Sound stimuli before filtering	54.5	81.5	44.3	77.5

2.3 Listening tests' subjects

The laboratory listening tests were performed by 40 people with age between 19 and 60 years old (32 male and 8 female tests subjects). Nobody from the tested people has reported severe hearing problems. All of them got the same instructions and description prior to the test from operator.

2.4 Listening test procedure

Laboratory listening tests were performed in a silent environment of a dedicated perception room ensuring low level of background noise. The laboratory was furnished as to resemble a living room environment.

The sound stimuli were presented via open, dynamic hi-fi stereo headphones, which are characterized by a particular spatial and dynamic sound image and whose playback frequency spectrum can be extracted from the technical specifications, in particular to ensure the relevant low frequency range to be reproduced in a correct manner. In order to play the stimuli with realistic sound levels (which would result from the given sound attenuation situation), the reproduction system was calibrated with an artificial ear.

During the test procedure, each lightweight construction situation was compared with each massive wall situation for each of the two sound stimuli, resulting in 64 comparative pairs per sound stimuli. Prior to the test runs, which were included in the evaluation, five “warm-up” comparisons were presented, in order to allow the test subjects to adjust to the test situation and operation of the test setup. The test subjects were able to play each sound from a pair as many times as they wish and their task was to determine either which of the presented stimuli sounded louder in comparison with the other one or if they were equally loud. The interface of the test program is shown in the Figure 1Figure 3.

Figure 3: Interface of the listening test program.

3. Single number quantities description

For the walls used as a filter for listening tests stimuli, single number quantities (SNQ) were calculated in order to characterize the sound insulation. The SNQ were determined according to the method specified in ISO 717-1 (R_w and $R_w + C_{50-5000}$, with frequency range extended down to 50 Hz). For the determination of R_{modMR} , the adapted reference hearing curve was used which corresponds to 90% subjects' individual thresholds in quiet [12]. However, only the lower part of spectra below 100 Hz of the reference curve according to ISO 717-1 has been modified. The reference curves are shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Reference curves used for calculation of SNQ-evaluation of sound insulation.

4. Results and discussion

Figure 5 shows the percentage of the listener answers for the stimuli sequence of the song “Highway to Hell” from ACDC that louder sound stimuli are conditioned by the sound insulation of the respective LW wall (green curve), or conditioned by the sound insulation of the respective HW wall (blue curve), or both are equally loud (black bars). The x-axis shows the corresponding wall combination pair (LW – HW wall).

Figure 6 is constructed in a similar way as Figures 5, only the stimuli sequence is done with pink noise.

Figure 5: Relative percentage of answers for the comparison of LW and HW walls during the presenting of stimuli sequence of ACDC – Highway to Hell.

Figure 6: Relative percentage of answers for the comparison of LW and HW walls during the presenting of stimuli sequence of pink noise.

After this analysis, LW-HW wall combination pairs that were found by listeners as equally loud were selected for each of the two sound stimuli. For the selected pairs, single number quantities (SNQ) were calculated with the spectra adaptation terms as described in chapter 3, e.g. R_w , $R_w + C_{50-5000}$ and R_{modMR} . For the calculated SNQ's, the difference between the corresponding sound insulation values between LW and HW walls were found. In the end the arithmetic mean and the standard deviation were calculated for these differences, e.g. the mean of the standard deviation of the function $|R_{LW} - R_{HW}|$ was found. The results can be seen in Table 2 (for Highway to Hell stimuli) and in Table 3 (for the pink noise stimuli).

Table 2: Arithmetic mean M and the standard deviation s of the sound insulation measures for stimuli that were evaluated as equally loud between LW and HW walls for the Highway to Hell sound stimuli.

	R_w	$R_w + C_{50-5000}$	R_{modMR}
M $ R_{LW} - R_{HW} $	3.72	2.69	2.49
s	2.47	2.09	2.09

Table 3: Arithmetic mean M and the standard deviation s of the sound insulation measures for stimuli that were evaluated as equally loud between LW and HW walls for the pink noise sound stimuli.

	R_w	$R_w + C_{50-5000}$	R_{modMR}
M $ R_{LW} - R_{HW} $	3.70	2.73	2.56
s	2.58	2.18	2.18

It is obvious that for both sound stimuli, using the R_{modMR} spectra adaption term for calculating the sound insulation of the walls gives the smallest arithmetic mean of the difference (the smallest error) between the two wall types, as well as the smallest standard deviation.

5. Conclusions

The results from the laboratory listening tests show that the approach of considering the abilities of hearing in the low frequency range at low sound levels results in the same SNQ also from the perception point of view. Despite the significantly different sound insulation characteristics of the two compared construction methods, the smallest differences in the singular data are obtained for the equally perceived wall combinations made of lightweight and heavyweight wall construction, if the spectrum close to 90% of the hearing threshold of test persons is used as a reference. The currently internationally accepted and standardized single number quantity combination $R_w + C_{50-5000}$ for evaluation of sound insulation have significantly different sound insulation perception. In terms of perception, these SNQ cannot be used for the comparison of lightweight and heavyweight construction.

With the use of R_{modMR} , the sound insulation value differences could be kept low and a perception-appropriate and construction-neutral characterization could be ensured.

Thus, it is also clear, that besides hitherto highly controversial choice of the stimulus spectrum, the sensitivity of the hearing plays an important role, especially if the low frequency range is included in the consideration. In addition, relatively low sound levels should be expected.

REFERENCES

- 1 Muellner, H.. Correlating Objective and Subjective Sound Insulation., *COST Action TU 0901 – Towards a common framework in building acoustics throughout Europe* (pp. 142-156). (2013).
- 2 Vian, J. P., Danner, W. F., Bauer, J. W. Assessment of significant acoustical parameters for rating sound insulation of partz walls. *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* 73 (4), pp. 1236-1243, (1983).
- 3 Hongisto, V., Oliva, D., Keränen, J. Subjective and Objective Rating of Airborne Sound Insulation–Living Sounds. *Acta Acustica united with Acustica* 100 (2014) 848-863 P., Giriūnienė, R., Rimeika, R. and Čiplys, D. Application of leaky surface acoustic waves for investigation of thin film properties, *Proceedings of the 18th International Congress on Sound and Vibration*, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil, 10–14 July, (2011).
- 4 Pedersen, D. B., Roland, J., Raabe, G., Maysenh, W. Measurement of the low-frequency sound insulation of building components, *Acta Acustica united with Acustica* 86 (3) pp. 495-505. (2000).
- 5 Mathys, J. Low-frequency noise and acoustical standards. *Applied Acoustics*, 40, pp. 185-199. (1993).
- 6 Rindel, J. H. Acoustic quality and sound insulation between dwellings. *Journal of Building Acoustics* 5, pp. 291-301. (1999).
- 7 Mortensen, F. R. Subjective evaluation of noise from neighbours with focus on low frequencies. *Main report, Publication no 53*, Department of Acoustic Technology, Technical University of Denmark. (1999).
- 8 Rindel, J. H. On the influence of low frequencies on the annoyance of noise from neighbours, *Proceedings internoise 2003*, Seogwipo, Korea. (2003).

- 9 Rasmussen, B. Sound insulation between dwellings – Classification schemes and building regulations in Europe. *Proceedings Inter-noise Prague*. (2004).
- 10 Rychtarikova, M., Muellner, H., Stani, M., Chemlik, V. & Glorieux, Ch. Does the Living Noise Spectrum Adaptation of Sound Insulation Match the Subjective Perception? *Proceedings Euro-noise 2012*, Prague, Czech Republic. (2012).
- 11 Rychtáriková, M., Muellner, H., Chmelík, V., Roozen, N. B., Urbán, D., Garcia, D. P., Glorieux, C. Perceived Loudness of Neighbour Sounds Heard Through Heavy and Light-Weight Walls with Equal $R_w + C_{50-5000}$. In *Acta Acustica united with Acustica*. Vol. 102, 2016, s. 58-66. ISSN 1610-1928.
- 12 Zwicker, E. *Psychoakustik*. Springer-Verlag, Berlin Heidelberg New York. (1982).